

SURVEILLANCE CARD RIFT VALLEY FEVER (RVF) - Pathogen detection in mosquitoes in areas of introduction risk

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	RVF virus identification in vectors present in the EU.
2	Surveillance aim	Early detection of the introduction of the pathogen.
3	Target species and group	<i>Aedes caspius</i> , <i>Aedes detritus</i> , <i>Aedes vexans</i> , <i>Culex pipiens</i> and <i>Culex theileri</i> (1).
4	Target sector / production type	Not applicable.
5	Geographical area covered	Whole country, water bodies specially those rich in areas with high vegetation index (favourable vector breeding sites).
6	Age group	Adult mosquitos and eggs.
7	Sampling point and strategy	Targeted sampling in areas with high expected mosquito abundance.
8	Sampling time period	Year-round but specially after heavy rainfalls, floods and when temperatures range between 15 °C to 24 °C (2).
9	Sampling matrix	Mosquitos and collected eggs.
10	Type of disease indicators	Virus detection.
11	Sampling unit	Pooled sample of vectors.
12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	Not applicable.
13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	In Mosquitos (3): 1. Mosquito collection and species identification Mosquitos should be morphologically identified to species (or genus) levels and after identification, stored in pools of the same species/genus, sex and sampling site. Blood-fed mosquitoes (with a visible blood meal in the abdomen) should be separated and stored individually.

		<p>2. RNA/DNA extraction Mosquitos are homogenized and centrifuged.</p> <p>3. Rift Valley fever phlebovirus detection using qRT-PCR Extracted RNA/DNA from blood-fed mosquitoes can additionally be used for blood meal analysis to infer host preferences of mosquito species.</p> <p>In Mosquito's eggs (4):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Egg raft husks and 1st instar larvae from the second (E2) and egg rafts from the third gonotrophic cycle (E3) are collected; 2. Collected samples are homogenized and centrifuged; <p>Detection of RVFV RNA via RT-qPCR.</p>
14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	Overall sensitivity of this surveillance component is likely to be low, because it is difficult to obtain representative samples of the mosquito population in a large geographic area. However, this component may be superior in timeliness to syndromic surveillance if the regions at risk are well defined.
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	West Nile Fever virus.
18	References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Drouin A, Chevalier V, Durand B, Balenghien T. Vector Competence of Mediterranean Mosquitoes for Rift Valley Fever Virus: A Meta-Analysis. <i>Pathogens</i>. 2022; 11(5):503. https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens11050503 2) Drakou, K., Nikolaou, T., Vasquez, M., Petric, D., Michaelakis, A., Kapranas, A., Papatheodoulou, A., & Koliou, M. (2020). The Effect of Weather Variables on Mosquito Activity: A Snapshot of the Main Point of Entry of Cyprus. <i>International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health</i>, 17(4), 1403. https://doi.org/10.3390/IJERPH17041403

		<ol style="list-style-type: none">3) Stoek, F., Barry, Y., Ba, A., Schulz, A., Rissmann, M., Wylezich, C., Sadeghi, B., Beyit, A. D., Eisenbarth, A., N'diaye, F. B., Haki, M. L., Doumbia, B. A., Gueya, M. B., Bah, M. Y., Eiden, M., & Groschup, M. H. (2022). Mosquito survey in Mauritania: Detection of Rift Valley fever virus and dengue virus and the determination of feeding patterns. <i>PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases</i>, 16(4), e0010203. https://doi.org/10.1371/JOURNAL.PNTD.00102034) Bergren, N. A., Borland, E. M., Hartman, D. A., & Kading, R. C. (2021). Laboratory demonstration of the vertical transmission of Rift Valley fever virus by <i>Culex tarsalis</i> mosquitoes. <i>PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases</i>, 15(3), e0009273. https://doi.org/10.1371/JOURNAL.PNTD.00092735) Petrova, V., Kristiansen, P., Norheim, G., & Yimer, S. A. (2020). Rift valley fever: diagnostic challenges and investment needs for vaccine development. <i>BMJ Global Health</i>, 5(8), e002694. https://doi.org/10.1136/BMJGH-2020-0026946) Wint, W., van Bortel, W., & Schaffner, F. (2020). RVF vector spatial distribution models: Probability of presence. <i>EFSA Supporting Publications</i>, 17(2). https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.en-1800
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